

Extraction and Characterization of Bio-oil from *Phoenix Dactylifera L.* (Date Palm Seed)Saddiq Maryam^{1*}¹Department of Chemistry, Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina, Nigeria.

maryam.saddiq@umyu.edu.ng.

Abstract

The study was carried out to extract oil from *phoenix dactylifera L.* (date palm seed) collected from Katsina town, Katsina State, Nigeria. Physicochemical parameters such as oil and moisture content, acid and saponification value were also determined. The sample was thoroughly cleaned and dried under shade for six (6) weeks. It was then crushed into powder using crushing machine. The extraction of oil from the ground seeds was done using n-hexane through soxhlet extraction method. The results showed that the percentage of oil yield was 28 % and the observed color of the oil was pale yellow with a mild nutty odor. The extracted oil was found to have a pH of 6.1 and a refractive index of 1.463. Chemical analysis revealed an acid value of 1.07 mg KOH/g and saponification value of 167.8 mg KOH/g indicating good oil quality and stability. FT-IR analysis confirmed the presence of functional groups characteristic of vegetable oils, including CH₂, C=O, C=C, C-C & C-O while the GC-MS analysis showed that the oil comprised mainly of low molecular weight fatty acids such as oleic acid, linoleic acid, lauric acid and palmitic acid and sterols such as β-sitosterol and stigmasterol. These findings confirmed that, date palm seed oil possesses favourable physicochemical properties which make it suitable for applications in food, cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries, thereby promoting the valorization of agricultural waste.

Keywords: Agricultural; Vegetable; Seed; Oil; Soxhlet.

1. Introduction

Date palm seeds, also known as date pits or stones are the hard, oblong kernels found within the fruit of the date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.). They constitute approximately 10–15% of the total weight of the date fruit and are typically considered a byproduct or waste in date processing industries. However, growing interest in sustainable practices and valorization of agro-industrial waste has led to increased research into their composition and potential applications (FAOSTAT, 2024). It is widely cultivated in tropical and subtropical regions, notably in the Middle East and North Africa (Qadir *et al.*, 2018). Globally, the gross production value of date fruits has been rising considerably since the 20th century, with the highest value seen at more than US \$14 billion in 2020 (FAOSTAT, 2024). Date palm trees and fruits drive the economic and social aspects of date-producing countries (Ghafoor *et al.*, 2022; Mrabet *et al.*, 2020). Date seeds, a by-product of date fruit production, are usually treated as waste, utilized as animal feed or just disposed of (Qadir *et al.*, 2018).

Oil extracted from date seeds is gaining attention due to its favorable fatty acid profile, which includes significant amounts of oleic, lauric and linoleic acids. Chemically, date seeds are rich in carbohydrates, dietary fiber, proteins, fats, and bioactive compounds, including phenolics and antioxidants (Habib *et al.*, 2013). In addition to oil extraction, date seeds have been studied for their potential in producing activated carbon, animal feed, dietary supplements, and as raw materials in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals industry (Niazi *et al.*, 2017; Sadiq *et al.*, 2013). Owing to its health benefits, date seeds possess high potential as a nutritional therapeutic agent for several chronic diseases (Hilary *et al.*, 2021). Given the global production of dates, particularly in Middle Eastern and North African countries, the sustainable utilization of date seeds represents an opportunity for economic and environmental benefits (Qadir *et al.*, 2018). Consequently, research into their extraction methods, physicochemical properties, and applications continues to expand (Al-Farsi & Lee, 2008).

2. Methodology

2.1 Sampling and Sample Pre-treatment

Received: 18 June 2026

Revised: 20 June 2026

Accepted: 22 June 2026

Copyright ♥ authors 2026

82

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26643/ijr/90>

Date fruits were collected from a date-producing area in Katsina city, Katsina, Nigeria in the month of October, 2025. After collection, seeds were separated manually from the fruits where only healthy, undamaged, and fully matured seeds were selected for the study in order to obtain the highest oil yield. The seeds were washed thoroughly so as to remove the peels and dried under shade for six (6) weeks. Thereafter, the seeds were crushed into a fine powder using crushing machine. The ground palm date seed was stored in an air tight container for further use.

2.2 Determination of Moisture Content

The total moisture content in the ground date palm seed was determined as described by Reddy *et al.* (2017).

2.3 Determination of Oil Content

The total moisture content in the ground date palm seed was also determined according to the procedure reported by Reddy *et al.* (2017).

2.4 Extraction of Oil

About fifty (50 g) grams of the ground seed was measured and transferred to a cellulose thimble and placed in a soxhlet extractor fitted with a condenser placed on a distillation flask containing n-hexane as the extracting solvent. The ground seed was then extracted under reflux for 5 h with 10 flushes and the sample was removed. Thereafter, n-hexane was evaporated using rotary evaporator under vacuum conditions. The extracted oil was allowed to cool down; the yield of the oil was recorded using the expression below;

$$\text{Yield of oil extraction} = \frac{\text{weight of sample after extraction}}{\text{weight of sample before extraction}} \times 100 \%$$

2.5 Determination of Acid value

Acid value is the mass of potassium hydroxide (KOH) in milligrams that is required to neutralize one gram of a chemical substance. It is a measure of the amount of carboxylic acid groups in a chemical compound. The acid value was determined by titrimetric analysis as described by Zhang *et al.* (2015). The acid value (AV) of the date seed oil was calculated using the expression below;

$$AV = \frac{V \times N \times 56.1}{W}$$

Where: V = Volume of KOH used (mL)

N = Normality of KOH (0.1 N)

W = Weight of oil sample (g)

56.1 = Molecular weight of KOH

2.6 Determination of Saponification Value

Saponification value is a measure of the amount of potassium hydroxide (KOH) required in order to hydrolyze one (1 g) gram of oil. The saponification value was determined by titrimetric method as described by Akbari *et al.* (2012). A blank experiment was carried out without the oil sample using the same procedure and reagents. The volume of HCl required for the blank was recorded. The saponification value (SV) expression is given by;

$$SV = \frac{(B - S)N \times 56.1}{W}$$

Where; B = Volume of KOH without oil (blank sample)

S = Volume of KOH with oil sample

N = Normality of KOH (0.1 N)

W = Weight of oil sample (g)

56.1 = Molecular weight of KOH

2.7 FT-IR Analysis

The Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) is utilized to study functional groups present in a liquid, solid and gaseous sample. The available functional groups present in the oil were recorded on an Agilent Technology's 630 FT-IR spectrophotometer. The sample was fixed in potassium bromide (KBr) disc and the sample was scanned in the range of 4000-650 cm^{-1} wavenumber.

2.8 GC-MS Analysis

The GC-MS analysis was employed to determine the fatty acid composition of the extracted oil from *phoenix dactylifera* L. using Agilent Technologies GC system with GC- 7890A/MS-5975C model (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, Ca, USA) equipped with HP-5MS column (30 m in length \times 250 mm in diameter \times 0.25 mm in thickness of film).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Moisture and Oil Content

The oil content of the date palm seed was about 20 % and the moisture content was about 9.5 % which were determined according to the procedure described by British Standards Institution (BS EN ISO 665: 2000 & 2009). The low moisture content was due to the fact that the seeds were

fresh and had enough time dry off. This value is in agreement with other studies were a value range between 3.1 -7.1 % moisture content was obtained (Amani *et al.*, 2013).

3.2 Oil yield and its Properties

Soxhlet extraction is the most cited technique in the literature used for extracting oil from date seeds and it is sometimes used as reference against other techniques because it gives the best yield of oil (Alem *et al.*, 2017). Hexane on the other hand, has been used for decades as solvents for fats and oils extraction from plant materials (Abdalla *et al.*, 2012). It has various qualities for easy extraction of lipids such as easily removal by evaporation, stability and convenient boiling point (Ali & El-Anany, 2025). The weight of the oil extracted was found to be 14 mL and the percentage (%) yield was 28 % based on dry matter. This is attributed to the extraction method, extracting solvent, solvent to sample ratio and extraction time. The result agrees with previous studies and the parameters studied contributed immensely in the yield of oil (Alem *et al.*, 2017; Al-Juhaimi *et al.*, 2018).

However, the oil was subjected to physicochemical analysis to determine its physical and chemical properties as shown in Table 3.1. Oil's appearance plays a crucial role in their potential applications. The color of the oil was pale yellow which looks similar to that of vegetable oil. Generally, vegetable oils color comes from the existence of coloring pigments such as β -carotene, chlorophyll and tocopherols (The & Birch, 2013). The saponification value (167.8 mg KOH/g) obtained was between that of palm kernel oil and coconut oil, which suggests that the oil may be suitable for soap production. The pH value of the oil was found to be 6.1, which shows that the oil is slightly acidic but acceptable. This suggests that the oil is relatively stable and not highly degraded. The refractive index is an indicative physicochemical parameter easy to get for oils and it was found to be 1.463. The low refractive index value indicated that their fatty acids may be composed of low molecular weight hydrocarbon chains. The acid value (1.07 mg KOH/g) of the oil indicates that the oil has low acidity. It is believed that, these bio-solvents produced from agricultural sources are greater potential candidates to replace petroleum solvents (Sicaire *et al.*, 2015; Breil *et al.*, 2016).

Table 3.1 Properties of the Extracted Oil

S/N	Property	Result
1	Weight	14
2	Percentage yield	28 %
3	Color	Pale yellow
4	Odor	Mild nutty

Received: 18 June 2026

Revised: 20 June 2026

Accepted: 22 June 2026

Copyright ♥ authors 2026

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26643/ijr/90>

5	Refractive Index	1.463
6	pH	6.1
7	Acid Value	1.07 mg/g
8	Saponification Value	167.8 mg/g

3.3 FT-IR Analysis

Table 3.2 shows the FT-IR spectrum of the oil extracted by n-hexane. From the FTIR analysis, it was observed that the result showed the following functional groups. Peak 1267 cm^{-1} region indicated the stretching vibration of C-O ester group and wagging of methylene (CH_2). The peak at 1756 cm^{-1} is assigned to the stretching vibration of carboxylic acid (C=O) group. Moreover, peak observed at 3324 cm^{-1} are due to bending and stretching vibration of O-H bonds. Peaks found at 2922 cm^{-1} is assigned to C-H stretching vibration and 1610 cm^{-1} was due to C=C stretching of alkene respectively. These functional groups confirm the presence of fatty acids and triglycerides in the oil and agree with previous studies conducted by Alem *et al.* (2017). Furthermore, the type of extracting solvent decides the nature of the extracted compounds from the sample (Thakur & Arya, 2014).

Table 3.2 Result of FT-IR Analysis of the Extracted Oil

Wave number (cm^{-1})	Functional group	Assignment
3324	Alcohol	O-H stretch
2922	Aliphatic	C-H stretch
1610	Alkene	C=C stretch
1267	Alkoxy	C-O stretch
1756	Carboxyl	C=O Stretch

3.4 GC-MS Analysis

Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry was employed to identify the fatty acid composition in the date palm seed oil. The result identified sixteen (16) compounds in the oil (Table 3.3) which include long chain fatty (saturated and unsaturated) acids and triglycerides. Oleic acid, β -sterol, linolenic acid and palmitic acid were present in substantial amount. Generally, oils with high oleic acid contents showed good flavor and frying stability and linolenic acid was reported to be crucial for the healthy growth of human skin. Previous studies on date palm seed by Akbari *et al.* (2012) have shown similar result.

Table 3.3 GC-MS Analysis of the Extracted Oil

Received: 18 June 2026

Revised: 20 June 2026

Accepted: 22 June 2026

Copyright ♥ authors 2026

S/N	Name of compound	RT	%
1	Capric acid	2.023	0.65
2	Caprylic acid	1.781	0.54
3	Lauric acid	2.413	7.89
4	Stearic acid	4.872	4.05
5	β -sitosterol	3.916	10.12
6	Eicosenoic acid	7.422	1.23
7	Linoleic acid	5.852	5.65
8	Oleic acid	4.791	40.38
9	Hexadecenoic acid	3.833	1.32
10	Palmitic acid	3.538	9.39
11	Tridecanoic acid	2.509	0.59
12	Pentadecanoic acid	2.792	0.82
13	Myristic acid	2.566	4.13
14	Stigmasterol	4.810	3.23
15	Linolenic acid	11.829	9.58
16	Palmitoleic acid	19.620	0.43

RT= retention time and %= percentage quality

4. Conclusion

Undoubtedly, the demand for plant-derived products has increased across the world. The study involves the extraction of oil from date palm seeds. The bio-oil obtained from date palm seed was very similar to other bio-oils in physicochemical properties. FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of important functional groups such as CH, C=O, C=C, O-H and C-O, which are characteristic of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids. This further confirms that the extracted oil is a typical vegetable oil with desirable chemical properties. GC-MS analysis of the oil identified sixteen compounds (16) with low molecular weight fatty acids and sterols having the highest percentage quality. Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that, date palm seed which is often regarded as waste, is a valuable source of oil with promising physicochemical characteristics, and its utilization can contribute to waste reduction and value addition.

References

- Abdalla, R. S. M., Albasheer, A. A., El-Hussein, A. R. M., & Gadkariem, E. A. (2012). Physicochemical characteristics of date seed oil grown in Sudan. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 9(7), 993-999. <https://doi.org/10.3844/ajassp.2012.993.999>
- Akbari, M., Razavizadeh, R., Mohebbi, G. H., & Barmak, A. (2012). Oil characteristics and fatty acid profile of seeds from three varieties of date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera*) cultivars in

- Bushehr- Iran. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 11(57), 12088-12093. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJB12.1084>
- Al Juhaimi, F., Özcan, M. M., Adiamo, O. Q., Alsawmahi, O. N., Ghafoor, K., & Babiker, E. E. (2018). Effect of date varieties on physico-chemical properties, fatty acid composition, tocopherols contents, and phenolic compounds of some date seed and oils. *Journal of food processing and preservation*, 42(4), e13584. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfpp.13584>
- Alem, C., Ennassir, J., Benlyas, M., Mbark, A. N., & Zegzouti, Y. F. (2017). Phytochemical compositions and antioxidant capacity of three date (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) seeds varieties grown in the South East Morocco. *Journal of the Saudi Society of Agricultural Sciences*, 16(4), 350-357.
- Al-Farsi, M. A., & Lee, C. Y. (2008). Optimization of phenolics and dietary fibre extraction from date seeds. *Food chemistry*, 108(3), 977-985. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2007.12.009>
- Ali, R. F., & El-Anany, A. M. (2025). Physico-chemical characteristics, nutritional quality, and oxidative stability of cold-pressed chia seed oil, date palm seed oil, along with their binary mixtures. *Cogent Food & Agriculture*, 11(1), 2466061.
- Amani, M. A., Davoudi, M. S., Tahvildari, K., Nabavi, S. M., & Davoudi, M. S. (2013). Biodiesel production from *Phoenix dactylifera* as a new feedstock. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 43, 40-43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2012.06.024>
- Breil, C., Meullemiestre, A., Vian, M., & Chemat, F. (2016). Bio-based solvents for green extraction of lipids from oleaginous yeast biomass for sustainable aviation biofuel. *Molecules*, 21(2), 196. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules21020196>
- FAOSTAT 2024. Statistical database. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data> Accessed April 10, 2024
- Ghafoor, K., Sarker, M. Z. I., Al-Juhaimi, F. Y., Babiker, E. E., Alkaltham, M. S., & Almubarak, A. K. (2022). Extraction and evaluation of bioactive compounds from date (*Phoenix dactylifera*) seed using supercritical and subcritical CO₂ techniques. *Foods*, 11(12), 1806. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11121806>
- Habib, H. M., Kamal, H., Ibrahim, W. H., & Al Dhaheri, A. S. (2013). Carotenoids, fat soluble vitamins and fatty acid profiles of 18 varieties of date seed oil. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 42, 567-572. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2012.06.039>
- Hilary, S., Kizhakkayil, J., Souka, U., Al-Meqbaali, F., Ibrahim, W., & Platat, C. (2021). In-vitro investigation of polyphenol-rich date (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) seed extract bioactivity. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 8, 667514. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2021.667514>

- Mrabet, A., Jiménez-Araujo, A., Guillén-Bejarano, R., Rodríguez-Arcos, R., & Sindic, M. (2020). Date seeds: A promising source of oil with functional properties. *Foods*, 9(6), 787. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9060787>
- Narender Thakur, N. T., & Vikrant Arya, V. A. (2014). Preliminary phytochemical analysis of the extracts of psidium leaves. 19(11), 1421-1424 .
- Niazi, S., Khan, I. M., Pasha, I., Rasheed, S., Ahmad, S., & Shoaib, M. (2017). Date palm: composition, health claim and food applications. *International Journal of Public Health and Health Systems*, 2(1): 9-17
- Qadir, A., Singh, S. P., Akhtar, J., Ali, A., & Arif, M. (2018). Chemical composition of Saudi Arabian Sukkari variety of date seed oil and extracts obtained by slow pyrolysis. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 80(5), 940-946. <https://doi.org/10.4172/pharmaceutical-sciences.1000441>
- Reddy, M. K., Rani, H. D., Deepika, C. N., Samrawat, S., Akshara, V., & Rajesh, K. (2017). Study on physicochemical properties of oil and powder of date palm seeds (*Phoenix dactylifera*). *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 6(12), 486-492.
- Sadiq, I. S., Izuagie, T., Shuaibu, M., Dogoyaro, A. I., Garba, A., & Abubakar, S. (2013). The nutritional evaluation and medicinal value of date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera*). *International journal of modern chemistry*, 4(3), 147-154.
- Sicaire, A. G., Vian, M., Fine, F., Joffre, F., Carré, P., Tostain, S., & Chemat, F. (2015). Alternative bio-based solvents for extraction of fat and oils: solubility prediction, global yield, extraction kinetics, chemical composition and cost of manufacturing. *International journal of molecular sciences*, 16(4), 8430-8453. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms16048430>
- Teh, S. S., & Birch, J. (2013). Physicochemical and quality characteristics of cold-pressed hemp, flax and canola seed oils. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis*, 30(1), 26-31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2013.01.004>
- Zhang, Q., Wu, J., Ma, P., Cai, J., & Zhang, Y. (2015). Acid value determination and preesterification of crude *Euphorbia lathyris* L. Oil. *World Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 3(02), 70-75. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/wjet.2015.32007>